

EQUALITY, EQUITY AND OPPORTUNITY

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The emphasis on individual achievement is highly regarded in the United States. No feature of our society is more prized than the opportunity for each person to reach his maximum potential. Most of us would like to believe that the humblest and poorest who are smart and gifted can lift up their heads and achieve new heights. The sky is the limit, in our folklore, not only in terms of becoming a super athlete like Tiger Woods or Alex Rodriguez, a captain of industry like Andrew Carnegie or Bill Gates, but also in becoming the president of U.S.—as with Andrew Jackson and Abe Lincoln who grew up in log cabins or in the case of Barack Obama who grew up in a broken home and is black.

But how intelligent were the hedge fund managers who earned hundreds of millions of dollars in one year? How much smarter are they compared to our teachers who earn a pittance in terms of what these managers made? Was the deciding factor brains? Or was it dad's connections that got them the job, and their cunning and competitive nature that gave them an edge over anybody who got in their way? Is that not the same type of person that recently put the global financial system at risk and in part caused the collapse of Main Street and shrinking of the middle class in Europe and the U.S.?

In our society does the individual's future income really depend on his own gifts or talent? What about heredity privilege and nepotism? What other factors play into the mix—and result in class differences? To what extent is there an alliance between the old rich and new dollars? Why do business people, with power and privilege, so often abuse the system, lie and cheat, and engage in fraudulent practices—at the expense of the masses or average American?

Maybe it has something to do with our historical DNA? Maybe Walt Whitman, more than 125 years ago, got it right in describing the economic turmoil of his era in *Democratic Vistas*. He recognized the nation's "almost maniacal appetite for wealth." He also noted the vulgarity of the success gene and the immoral underpinnings of the prowealth and capitalist class. How does society correct the gross corruptible practices on Wall Street and in banking which lead to gross inequalities? What kind of restraints need to be imposed on the powerful and privileged in order to prevent the likes of "Enronism," and Madoff—and ensure "life, liberty, and pursuit of happiness" for working Americans? What kind of restraints are needed so that the prowealth drive is curbed and doesn't lead to excesses which usually piles up against plain people who are just trying to make ends meet.

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The issues that have been raised will not go away, at least not in our democratic and heterogeneous society—and not in our competitive society; they directly affect the social fabric of the country and the notions of social mobility, education opportunity, and economic outcomes of life. While we need to examine differences between excellence and equality, and the need to achieve some balance in a democratic society, we should also distinguish between equality and equity. The powerful and troubling analysis of equality and equity persist, best analyzed today by Nathan Glazer and Christopher Jencks—Harvard professors and sociologists who have spent a lifetime studying inequality as it relates to race and class.

Forget the platitudes of the American dream. There is no equality or equity when the drive for power or money, under the guise of achievement or success, run amok. What we need to do is to curb the unabashed and zealous ambitions of wealth, the so-called business and Wall Street drive for success; then the issues of equality and equity will fall into place, then the dream is achievable. Although this may seem too nuanced for some readers, the simple truth is that great inequality of wealth hinders equality and equity and leads to a financial oligarchy which subsequently corrupts government.

Equality has to do with similarity in opportunity or results, but *equity* (or fairness) deals with a person's or group's effort and the reward (or outcomes) for that effort. Inequality occurs when a person or group works harder but achieves little reward or, reverse, when a person or group works less and receives most of the rewards. Someone who is unqualified or unable to perform at prescribed levels cannot expect to achieve the same results given the same effort as a highly qualified person. Of course, the race card or the notion of victimization has been used in the past to neutralize the lack of qualifications. With rising expectations of groups who define themselves as a political minority (previously discriminated against and now entitled to certain benefits or preferential treatment), the expectations become politicized and society is forced to compromise, negotiate or litigate.

Equal Opportunity—For Whom?

Inequality involves a lack of opportunity, whereby the laws and/or social institutions discriminate against certain people or groups based on a perceived characteristic; henceforth, those people will be disadvantaged in society. To be sure, the design of society—equal opportunity or unequal opportunity—determines what happens to people in education, jobs, healthcare, housing, etc. and how income and wealth will be distributed among people.

Excessive inequality negatively impacts on economic growth and productivity. Just as discrimination results in a nation not making the best use of its citizens, inequality leads to inadequate schooling and housing, and inadequate funding of infrastructure. Many at the bottom, even at the middle, are unable to live up to their potential because those at the top of the pyramid strive to put limitations on taxation and income redistribution. By doing so, they impede investments in public education and housing, as well as infrastructure—and thus slow down growth and productivity. As inequality grows, the effects become more public and partisan—whereby the rich and powerful implement policies that favor the money class at the expense of the bottom half or even bottom 90 percent—and nation as a whole. The reelection of President Obama represented a battle against inequality—a revolt against Wall Street, and against the rich and super rich in the U.S.

By considering *opportunity*, the question ultimately arises who gets what jobs and what rewards. If a discriminatory pattern exists—based on race, religion, ethnicity or gender—then conflict is going to eventually arise. The more evident the inequality, the greater the chances for conflict in a democratic society. The more *egalitarian* the society, the more evenly distributed are earnings among its citizens and the more likely pay differences can be settled through compromise.

In a highly diverse society like ours, any group that defines itself as a political minority will become sensitive to group differences in test scores, educational achievement levels, economic outcomes—and demand

modifications that move society toward equalization. Members of the larger society may have to water down standards, but the other alternative is continuous dispute and conflict. Questions arise whether the new standards will influence striving for excellence and whether the change in standards is justified in terms of penalizing high-performing members of society or helping members of society who have experienced past discrimination. The first part of the question has long-term economic implications and the second part has moral implications.

Here we are not attempting to achieve an equal result, which ignores the concept of effort or ability and assumes that everyone is entitled to equal rewards, regardless of effort or ability. Such an assumption has more to do with affirmative action and quotas. With equity, we are seeking some sort of fairness. We want to avoid a stacked deck, the existence of inequality and inequity—no matter what their effort or ability some people will always be discriminated against. The potential effects are more than just economic or moral; the outcomes have social, political, and emotional consequences, resulting among the disenfranchised in feelings of inferiority, anger, self-hatred, and hatred of others, and producing pathological and delinquent behavior (in terms of crime, delinquency, and drugs), and detrimentally affects the productivity and vitality of the nation. If a person cannot find viable work, if the deck is stacked against a person, the argument can be made: Why go to school? Why try to find a job? The system is unfair and unjust; it is easier to drop out.

When we talk about equal opportunity, eventually the question arises as to whether everyone should have the right to go to college. If everyone has the right to a high school education, why not college? But the pool of abilities and talent varies, and there are many children whose academic limitations cannot be traced to poverty or deprivation. Children who come from upper-class homes have the advantage of social capital, and have parents who can hire private tutors, if necessary, and have the ability to move to a successful school district—where schools are cleaner and more modern, where teachers are better paid and generally have more education and experience, and the school climate is more conducive to learning.

Others who are less fortunate start out on a less than equal footing and continue to experience family, school, peer group, and community handicaps that only increase their disadvantages—and thus are often doomed to disappointment. A *culture of poverty* exists in the United States, a term first popularized by Oscar Lewis in *La Vida*; where before poverty is passed on from one generation to the next—as if these people were living in an underdeveloped country. They become maligned as modern-day primitives, allowed to live on welfare or near poverty levels, and allowed to exist in and journey through a parallel Hobbesian world.

College and Class

Despite ability or talent, children who come from advantaged homes have parents with a network of political and social connections as well as alumni and business-related friends by birth or social status that help get their children into Ivy League colleges and high-paying jobs. Competition for good jobs requires that you get into the right university, not just a university. According to former Harvard President Lawrence Summers, “Just 3 percent of students at the nation’s top 146 colleges come from families in the bottom socioeconomic quartile,” that is the bottom 25 percent. These figures were echoed in a 2006 higher education report that less than ten percent of the students in the most selective colleges come from the bottom half of the income scale, whereas 74 percent come from the top quarter, evidencing market disparities based on income. The inference here is that the bottom half of the income scale of student population is either stupid, a rehash of Spencerism and the genetic school of thought that dominated late nineteenth and first half of the twentieth century thinking, or that prestigious institutions of higher learning discriminate against students on the basis of tuition and price out the majority of applications because of financial need.

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Brian Berry of Columbia University spins the same point in *Why Social Justice Matters*. Some 35 percent of undergraduates at Princeton are from “non-sectarian private school: over 20 times their 1.7 percent in school population.” These figures may be slightly higher than the average for other elite universities, “but not a lot out of line with the others.” You don’t have to be a rocket scientist to get into Yale or Harvard or to work on Wall Street, and many people who accumulate the usual clutch of mansions, fancy cars, and millionaire baubles possess fewer abilities and are “C” students. Ironically, the business world is depressingly full of millionaires, who ignore their head start in life and equate their net worth with brains, that is wealthy boys and girls born on third base who think they hold the major league record for triples.

If we need, still another compass to direct our thinking, then we live in a divided world of unbridled materialism, consumerism, and excess on one end of the spectrum and massive slosh of poverty, deprivation, and blight on the other end. It’s not much different than how the patricians and plebeians see the world: Those who belong to a “blue-blood, old boys” club and those who do not; those who believe their ancestors amassed great fortunes from their brains and guts and those on the other side who are convinced the captains of industry, yesterday and today, made their money by trampling on the downtrodden and ripping off the consumer; those who get their first job in Wall Street with major investment firms and those who are regulated to get their first job in a small-town bank as a bank teller or assistant to the branch manager; people who are welcomed in the stateliness of the Episcopal Church and other people who listen to the sermons of the untutored clergy of the less prestigious dominations and sects.

The fact is rich children with average SAT scores, and whose parents are well connected, manage to get into an Ivy League school while those with above average test scores are content with being accepted to a good state university. Colleges often say they are not backing away to attract low-or moderate-income students. In fact, some institutions espouse a twisted logic by saying they take more students who can afford to pay full or nearly full tuition in order to recruit and better serve those who cannot. But the reality is that there is a limit on how many needy students can be admitted and they are often wait listed and dropped to less prestigious and less expensive colleges. Wealthy students have a distinct advantage of being admitted, and only very wealthy institutions with endowments in the billions can afford, today, to be need-blind. But let’s be clear about class and connections. Attending Harvard or Yale is part of the “old-boy network” and “blue-blood club” that permits “C” students the opportunity to rise above their potential—and possibly wreck a company or country—not only in the United States but also in any place in the world.

We would like to believe that those who attend Harvard or Yale might take the position that their education is not designed to make them rich, and that the majority of Ivy League graduates do not want to walk in some super-duper law firm in Boston or New York or work on Wall Street and earn hundreds of thousands or millions of dollars a year. We would like to think that a sizeable number would think about public service and other careers (in health, education, and science) beyond the legal and financial world, and the high-priced consulting, lobbyist and guest-speaking world. The number of Ivy League students wanting to work on Wall Street (approximately 50 percent) reached its all-time high just before the bubble burst in 2008.

During the “meltdown,” some hot areas were venture capital, overseas companies, and energy. For the good of the nation, we would like to believe that talent would shift from pinstripes to lab coats, from moving money to building bridges and investing in green technology—and that there would be a revival of the Sputnik era, when the talented chose science and engineering. But our values get in the way. As the market rebounds, high-achieving (“type A” students) will most likely enter a new race to Wall Street, banking and white-shoe law firms.

Somehow, I do believe that many Ivy League students start out idealistic, wanting to change the world for the better or to make a mark in some creative endeavor. Yet, the lure of “big bucks” and a big house, that is the trappings of “success,” and the conversations of classmates and friends about money, money, and more money take

its toll on idealism and service-oriented careers. We live in a highly materialistic society, driven by greed (softened by the word “ambition”), conspicuous consumption (softened by “consumer spending”), and corruption (softened by the words “reality” or “politics”).

It is hard to say no to the world of unfettered capitalism, as opposed to egalitarianism or social justice, when you are being recruited with fancy dinners and starting six-figure salaries. At Wall Street, top tier-talent with MBAs start at \$300,000, and with bonuses at \$450,000, according to the 2010 *Private Equity Compensation Report*. It’s real easy to sit behind a computer and apply for 25 or 30 jobs, put down your Harvard or Yale credentials, and wait for E-mail messages to bounce on your screen. It’s much easier, or at least more practical, to use your talent and abilities to gain financial security than to serve your community or country—and that has to do something with the values of our society. To be sure, the rich are better off than the poor or working man—not because they are made of better stuff, but because they are spared the indignity of always needing a hand out, always asking for a 50 cent raise, always living paycheck to paycheck.

We would like to believe in the image of a person who rose from nothing and who owed nothing to parentage. This is part of the American dream and the notion of the self-made person (usually a man); and there is just enough possibility and truth in these stories, a testimony to American democracy. But the humblest and poorest rarely rise to the top. Statistically the odds do not coincide with popular literature or folklore. Their main interest and most realistic aspiration is survival, not success. Still, we would also like to believe that an under achiever in school, someone with average or even less than average abilities could rise to fame and fortune through hard work and luck. Also, we would like to believe that people with brains or brawn can still achieve the American Dream. It’s the perfect antidote for a country reeling from an underachiever, who got into Yale because of daddy’s alumni status, and who rose to fame and fortune because of political connections, powerful friends, and patronage.

But most underachievers sleep walk through life, especially those who engage in muddled thinking and have trouble completing whole sentences in the public arena; in short, most “C” students have difficulty adjusting to a complex society, where extensive information must be understood and complex judgments and decisions must be made. (The answer is not to brag that you speak to God or make decisions by gut feeling.) While democracy releases the energy and talents of every human being, heredity privilege rewards ignorance and puts a lid on aspirations and the pursuit of excellence. No question in our society, “hidden gifts” and special talent can be discovered—and the popular literature is full of such images.

But for every poor or working-class person, for every “C” student that becomes a governor or president, a captain of industry or a super athlete, hundreds of thousands are doomed to live out their life in the same income quintile they started, or slightly move, an inch or two higher. (During a twenty-five year period, ending in 2012, 60 percent of families in the lowest income quintile remained at the same level. In reverse, 59 percent in the highest income quintile remained at the same level.) Given a highly competitive society, life is not a bowl of cherries or a rose garden and sometimes there is more rain than sunshine. All you have to do is listen to the songs of Muddy Waters, A.P. Carter, and Johnny Cash—and you hear a prickle or sad story about the human condition and reality of life.

Knowledge/Information Society

The phrase “postindustrial society” coined in 1973 by Harvard’s Daniel Bell, in *The Coming of Post-Industrial Society*, describes the scientific-technological societies evolving in industrialized countries in the second half of the twentieth century. The singular feature of this society is the importance of scientific, mathematical and technical knowledge as the source of production, innovation, and policy formulation. Emerging from the older economic systems in both advanced capitalistic and socialistic countries is a *knowledge* and *Information* society

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based on preeminence of professionals and managers. In the United States during the 1950s and 1960s, Bell notes, “this group outpaced...all others in rate of growth, which was...seven times more than the overall rate for workers.”

Reflecting the paradigm shift of the times, University of Chicago President Robert Hutchins wrote an overstuffed and stiff book, *The Learning Society*, geared for the academic mind—and not for mass consumption. In the book, he predicted that the knowledge industry was producing a host of professionals and technocrats such as scientists, engineers, researchers and financial analysts who would take economic advantage of this new paradigm or shift impacting on society. Moreover, the effect of the knowledge revolution was “to accelerate technical change without thought of its social consequences.” Today, the technological revolution has created economic opportunities for entrepreneurial and gifted people—way beyond their imagination, intellectual capabilities, and levels of education might suggest.

In the 1990s computer and high-tech sectors outpaced the entire economy, reflected by a soaring NASDAQ market whose bubble burst in 2000. Nonetheless, the stratification structure of this new society has produced a highly trained, knowledge-based elite, which was supported by a large scientific, mathematical and technical staff and which became the economic engine for the new century. Moreover, it is only the part of society that successfully competed on a large scale with the patrician (super-rich) society, at least up to the point where the “blue bloods” have taken notice of who is being admitted into Harvard and working on Wall Street, as well as what are the latest trends in Silicon Valley or North Carolina’s “Golden Triangle.”

Bolstered by free markets and an unregulated system of capitalism, the wing of the knowledge industry that became affiliated with Wall Street and the banking industry helped create a global financial system that few people understood and depended on “knowledgeable” and ethical people to manage and protect their pensions and savings. This led to a new cottage industry including TV programs like “Squawk Box,” “Fast Money” and “Nightly Business Report” and pundits from the likes of Larry Kudlow and Jim Cramer to the “spin master,” Alan Greenspan, the former chair of the Federal Reserve—who were supposed to provide Americans with an informed analysis of financial and economic trends.

The new financial programs and pundits, armed with sophisticated financial formulas and statistical models, helped create an interconnected global economy and a new mindset on Wall Street and in banking based on greed, corruption and fraud. It was riddled with the bundling of toxic mortgages to disguise their limited value, short selling and the hollowing out of healthy companies, bogus accounting statements, outrageous bonuses to executives who often crippled their own companies because of excess risk, selling and buying of derivatives or insurance guarantees that could not be paid and falsified ratings of companies which were on the verge of bankruptcy. Instead of carrying out their traditional role as the stewards of money, many traders and brokers risked the money of clients and stockholders. The outcome was the Great Recession—massive losses of public and private pensions and personal savings of ordinary Americans, nearly \$7 trillion in stocks and \$8 trillion in housing value—a total of \$15 trillion. In short, the new mindset unleashed and magnified America’s rise of inequality, the decline of manufacturing and labor, and the waning of the middle class.

With the benefits of hindsight, the reverberations from the downturn in the global markets has led to an overall weakened American economy and a dispirited nation. The only people who recovered were the top 1 percenters. For example, their wages increased 13 percent in 2010, from 7 percent in 1979. In the meantime the median income for working households decreased 12.5 percent from 2000 to 2011.¹ Moreover, the economic decline of the working and middle class has led to increased strife throughout the world as emerging and developing nations who were dependent on American consumers felt the ripple effects that have undermined American

¹ Steven Greenhouse, “Productivity Climbs, But Wages Stagnate,” *New York Times*, January 13, 2013, p. SR 5.

prosperity. To be sure, the driving force behind this financial collapse has been the old desire for money and quick profits, but part of the blame must be shouldered by the knowledge industry—so called professionals, with their advanced degrees and expectations to earn a lot of money, who ignored risk and was sucked into the casino-like atmosphere.

A Change in Meritocracy

The basis of achievement in the postindustrial society is education and high academic expectations. Merit and differentials in status, power, and income are awarded to highly educated and trained experts with credentials; they are seen as the decision makers who will inherit the power structure in business, finance, government, and even politics. Achievement and mobility are also related to entrepreneurship and risk taking: What Ben Franklin would call hard work and Goldman Sachs or *Forbes* magazine might call “making money the old-fashioned way.” In a book called *Class: A Guide Through the American Status System*, Paul Fussell, a University of Pennsylvania sociologist, labeled these postindustrial “knowledge workers” as the “X class.”

William H. Whyte, the author of *The Organization Man*, one of the most significant nonfiction books of the 1950s, said the middle-class person was “always somebody’s man” whereas the X person is nobody’s. X people are highly independent, educated, and achievement oriented: “Retirement being a concept meaningful only to hired personnel or wage slaves who despise their hard work.” It might also be said that X people are more tolerant and can negotiate the color line that has run smack through American history—adding to the notion of the American dream; or to borrow from the words of Lorraine Hansberry, “Look what the new world hath wrought.”

This trend toward a meritocracy of the intellectual elite has aggravated inequalities. The majority of people in a democratic society accept this form of inequality, because it is based on individual talent and achievement—not inherited privilege or rank—and because this form of meritocracy is designed, at least in theory, to benefit the common good. Because of socioeconomic deprivation and limited education, poor and working-class groups are unable to compete successfully in a society based on educational credentials and educational achievement. Without the appropriate certificates, they are not needed by the economy; not necessarily exploited, but underpaid for their services; not necessarily discriminated against, but not in demand; not necessarily misfits as in Hobbesian world, but not able to easily climb the tree of American life.

The knowledge and information industry has raised education requirements for jobs. Those that were formerly filled by elementary training now demand high school graduates, and those that were formerly filled by secondary training now require a college degree. To be sure, there is a casual connection between education and jobs, which encourage parents to save and send their children to college. However, many social scientists argue that bright students and well-to-do students stay in school longer, inferring that the *cause-effect* relationship to jobs is not schooling, rather IQ and income. Likewise, if employers have a choice between hiring an uneducated and educated person, the latter will be chosen not necessarily because he or she will perform better rather education levels are an easy way to sort out candidates for jobs. The assumption is the schools have performed the sorting out process for the employer.

In a society that prizes merit and achievement, the reward structure is linked to a person’s natural ability. In *The Rise of Meritocracy*, Michael Young warned that such a society would put most of its resources in effective programs and schools that favored the academic elite, thus pushing the gifted and talented to the top and the less gifted and talented behind. Even worse, the process would continue over generations because of the assertive and class-based mating and the component of heredity, which people in a democracy prefer not to discuss because of its ethnic and racial implications. Both bright and slow students and adults will continue to compete in school and society, partially fortified by class distinctions (environment) and heredity. Barring drastic government policies, the

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search for merit and achievement will move capable people to the top and less capable people to the bottom. Although some say this is the most ideal-type society, as it gives everyone the chance to rise to the top, it has serious implications for average and dull people, and with people who have fewer opportunities because of lower or working class backgrounds. If left unchecked or unregulated, it leads to increasing inequality, and ultimately where one group feels they belong to another species—very high or very low.

If there is a stranger word than whoops, it applies here: When smart people come to believe that their success is based on skill, achievement and hard work, and the absence of patronage, nepotism, or discrimination. Even worse is when they fail to recognize that luck, both good or bad, is a major factor in determining economic outcomes. Eventually they justify their income and wealth, and any degree of inequality that comes about due to meritocracy. Here is Young again, writing a 2001 *Guardian* news article called “*Down with Meritocracy.*”

If people come to believe their advancement is based on their merits, “they can feel they deserve whatever they can get. They can be insufferably smug,” more so than someone who knows their advancement is based on politics or discrimination. “The newcomers can actually believe they have morality on their side. So assured have the [new] elite become that there is almost no block on the rewards they arrogate to themselves.” Thus inequality becomes more grievous as the years pass, and no one seems to raise questions. In this light, meritocracy based on achievement cannot fully justify large rewards which create significant inequality.

Merit and Class Bias

A new form of arrogance can develop by the creation of meritocracy, by the same people who once believed in and exemplified the political theories of Jeffersonian democracy and the stories of Horatio Alger. If true merit becomes associated with heredity or innate ability, as it often is construed, as opposed to the notion of opportunity, than meritocracy becomes less of a virtue and more of a propaganda tool for patricians and conservatives to wave and use against the populace who have fewer opportunities (and less luck) because their social and economic status. An achievement-oriented society based on academic credentials and standardized tests (which compare individuals in relation to a group score, say on IQ, achievement, or aptitude) condemns many people who cannot compete on an intellectual or cognitive level to the low end of stratification structure. It is a classic problem: The rich (who have more resources for better education) get richer and the poor get poorer—and gaps between the “haves” and “have nots” have dramatically increased in the last decade.

Put in more precise terms, for the last thirty years, one-fifth of the population (on the income pyramid) has been improving its prospects while the remaining 80 percent has lagged behind. With the former Bush administration, it was the top 10 percent that glommed almost all of the economic growth because of an expanding world economy, Wall Street get-rich schemes, and free-market economic policies—and which created unstable conditions for working-and middle-class people. A few economists such as Paul Krugman and Robert Reich would argue, as I would, that the top 1 percent were the real beneficiaries of the Bush tax cuts. It was greed and corruption that characterized Wall Street and many parts of the banking and home mortgage industry, in turn, which led to the bubble bursting in 2008—causing tens of millions of Americans to lose their jobs and houses (as of 2013 some 23 million Americans were unemployed or underemployed, and 20% of U.S. house mortgages were under water). The bubble turned into a world-wide recession because of an interconnected global banking system and global trade system that was falsely propped up by American consumerism and American debt.

Surprisingly, no one has rebelled, although discontent is mounting. The majority of the populace have not imposed higher taxes on the wealthy; in fact, the opposite has occurred, partially because conservative forces since the Nixon administration have dominated the White House or Congress. Only with the Obama administration, and a democratic Congress, did society seriously contemplate methods for reducing inequality in income and wealth between the rich and the rest of us. **The outcome was that...**

In education terms, however, what counts today is how the government spends money on intellectual capital—federal support of schools, college scholarships, retraining of labor, etc. Human capital (educated and credentialed professionals and business people) is the key for creating economic capital. Should Alexander Hamilton’s mob be educated (his view of the common people), and to what extent? In the final analysis, human capital (Thomas Jefferson’s position) is more important than economic capital (Hamilton’s position) if democracy is to survive and if the country is going to continue to prosper. The irony is, however, inequality is exacerbated by the rise of human capital, that is, by an increase of knowledge workers. Inequality is greater in cities such as New York, Boston, and Los Angeles because knowledge workers easily find work in these cities and earn considerably more than people who engage in routine tasks, or low-tech and low-end jobs. But the other side of the coin is that knowledge workers contribute more to society and therefore deserve to be paid more. In simple economic terms, how much more can we raise the salary of an *expert* janitor—\$1/hr, \$2/hr? Consider the janitor’s raise vis-a-vie the raise for an expert computer programmer, scientist or attorney.

In today’s knowledge society, there are several “intangibles” that cannot be measured in terms of value or predict how they may be used in the future. Patents, trademarks, copyrights and brand names are intangibles that have real value in an information and innovative society, but they cannot be judged on a balance sheet. The same holds true in trying to assess a company’s research and development, managerial expertise, marketing and advertising ability—that is the intellectual property it owns. These intangibles do not coincide with accounting procedures in terms of income or expenses, credits or debits, assets or liabilities.

Although these intangibles have no agreed market value today, they can make or break a company (or person), given the nature of competition and free markets, and the new economy based on information and technology. Reformers and leading business schools talk about a new “triple bottom line” in terms of “people, planet and profit.” But that doesn’t really help in determining the potential worth of a company’s or person’s intangible assets. We are at the early stages of defining or redefining innovation in a knowledge society as well as specific fields of knowledge. Given the complexity of our society, we are dependent on many kinds of talents, many kinds of achievement, and many kinds of knowledge and complex judgments. In the new economy, all this know-how and all this intellectual property boils down to future jobs—mostly middle-class, white collar jobs—and national wealth.

Americans now produce fewer and fewer products; however, we produce intellectual property (i.e. pharmaceutical research, computer chips, software, etc.) which has dramatically increased the nation’s innovative, information and high-tech economy. This type of intellectual capital has led to millions of new jobs and opportunities, the most important reason for focusing on human capital. In some respects, human capital is more important than economic capital because the latter is limited to a fixed amount. Developing human capital, on the other hand, permits us to address society’s present and future problems; its potential for creating wealth is limitless.

Bill Gates, who blends Jefferson’s politics with Hamilton’s economics, is critical of the nation for rationing education on wealthy and suburban children at the expense of low-income and urban children. He has personally committed \$1.2 billion for high school reform that would ensure that all students he funds receive a college prep curriculum. The fact is, however, the human capital agenda starts at the prekindergarten level, the developmental age when cognitive development is rapid and considered a foundation for future growth and development. In fact, according to Benjamin Bloom, in *Stability and Change in Human Characteristics*, 50 percent of potential for learning has been developed by age 4, another 25 percent by age nine, and the remaining 25 percent by age 17. This suggests that infant education, kindergarten and the primary grades (1-3) are essential in terms of nurturing student achievement—and where education dollars should be allocated.

Will the efforts of Bill Gates and other reformers help achieve a more meritorious society? People are human, complicated by a host of flaws including greed and arrogance. If those who advance come to believe they

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have achieved economic success strictly on their own merits, they may come to believe they are entitled to what they get—and the hell with stupid, slow or average people. Many newcomers of wealth, the academic elite and knowledge-based people, actually come to believe they have morality, justice and the common good of society on their side. But all their propositions can be construed as nothing more than old-fashion Spencerism—the notion of “survival of the fittest” and the evolutionary process that favors the stronger and smarter animal or person, and the law of nature that reinforces the doctrines of classical economists. The idea is that success is tied to some innate ability or heritable gene is the modern version of the preaching of success which has become an honored profession since the vogue of Horatio Alger who wrote 119 books idealizing success, the sentiment you can’t keep a good man down, “and every man has a goose that lays golden eggs, if he only knew it.”

Of course, historically, the masses are still handicapped by the inherent political, social and monetary advantage of the rich: People born on the more fortunate side of the economic divide who use their parent’s economic resources and social connections to rise up the ladder of success. The old rich do not need to rely on education or effort, intelligence or talent, to pass their wealth on to their offspring. They do not need a theory of natural abilities or gene for success that extends from one generation to the next. They have relied on cunning, drive and reward-risk thinking, coupled with many other factors (including past fraud and theft which is often camouflaged as commercial drive and success and) that have little to do with problem solving or abstract thinking. They have taken advantage of geography, timing and luck—and inheritance. They have the natural advantage of wealth, which supersedes talent or merit. Education is no longer the great equalizer, at least not in the twenty-first century. It cannot match or stand up to extreme inequalities of income and wealth. The catch up process involves several generations, moreover tax policies favor wealth (assets already in place) and discriminate against salaries and wages which are taxed at higher rates than earnings from wealth. Only if inequalities of income and wealth are kept within narrow ranges can education help in equalizing differences between the rich and rest of us.

Conclusion

There is no absolute method for recognizing talent and merit. Trying to figure out the interactions of environment and heredity is a hopeless policy issue, rather the crux of the problem is to deal with social disadvantages related to class factors that twist and deform the spirit and lead to the plight of the next working-class generation—people who will barely earn enough to tread water, pay their bills, and hopefully not go too deeply in debt. For example, in 2011 the average American had plastic debt of more than \$10,000—and that figure includes a vast swarth of people who think they are middle class.

We need to find a balance, some entitlement or safety net that protects working people or ordinary people while identifying and rewarding performance. Part of the search for balance (or fairness) is to adopt an uncompromising commitment to produce a society which permits the great masses to rise under conditions of social and economic mobility. Motivating the masses to achieve, and allowing them some opportunity to do so, is the driving force that has resulted in the rise of America as a super power. To reduce inequality, however, we need to increase opportunity among the bottom 90 percent and tax luck—not achievement or talent. We need only to clarify what percentage of person’s economic outcome is related to luck.

It should be clear that we do not want a society that leads to quotas or equality of results based on reverse discrimination. Similarly, we do not want a society that encourages unbridled competition where most of the rewards go to a few. Statistically, overtime, we will wind up with the same “winners” and “losers” in schools and on the job, and many losers will eventually drop out of school and society. There is no magic formula, no agreed set of recommendations for balancing or achieving both excellence and equality. The nuances are too complex to please the entire American populace. Perhaps someone in a little cabaret in South Texas (a Johnny Cash jingo) or a coffee shop in Hoboken, New Jersey (a Philip Roth location) or a church in Yoknapatawpha County (William Faulkner’s fictional but real place) can figure out a solution, as our leaders and statesmen cannot come to a consensus, and

instead regularly engage in nabobs of negativism. All we can hope for is some balance—some sense of fairness in the search for talent and in the reward system that drives society, and some sense of fairness in the distribution of wealth.

We don't have to bash Bush and Cheney—now seemingly nothing more than “tweedledum and tweedledee,” two peas in the pool. We don't have to lionize FDR, LBJ or Obama as champions of the little people. All we have to do is abolish just a few social and economic hierarchies that stratify society and create differences in income and wealth. We need to provide programs that protect slow runners and curb the swift; the idea is not to tax performance but the variance related to inheritance. We also need to create a floor and ceiling on income and wealth, one that is linked to the common good and not the whims of business executives who cook their company books to create the illusion of profits. In general this is the path to equality. The other way—the free market system without checks and balances—is simply to let individual differences, based on a mix of hereditary status, social privilege, and merit (and also some larceny) determine the outcomes. Without restraints or regulation, extremes and abuses will characterize society under the guise of competition and merit. The outcome is, a society fueled by the ideas of Darwin, Spencer and Ayn Rand that can be traced to the old world—the early warlords and nobility class.